

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance at The Kutambaru District Office

Edy Anta Tarigan¹, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Magister Manajemen, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Email Correspondence: ediantatigan@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office. This research was carried out at the Kutambaru District Office. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 15 employees with ASN and honorary status at the Kutambaru District Office. The sampling technique in this study used the entire population of 15 people. The research results show that Transformational Leadership has a significant influence on employee performance as shown by the T-Statistic value of $4.104 > 1.753$ and the P Value of $0.001 < 0.05$. This shows that improvements in Transformational Leadership can improve employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office.

Keywords: Transformational leadership; Employee performance

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important assets in a company organization. In order to produce high performance, human resources must be considered, maintained and developed. Performance is the most important thing in human resource management that needs to be managed well, because evaluation of work performance or employee performance is a measure of the success of human resources in the company. An employee's performance will be seen from how an employee shows his work performance, this is accompanied by a sense of responsibility for his duties and work. The role of leadership in improving the performance of educational organizations. Leadership in the world of education has a crucial role in shaping the direction, culture and effectiveness of an institution (Purwoko et al., 2022).

The North Sumatra Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) has a crucial role in disaster management efforts in its region. As an agency responsible for managing and handling disasters, North Sumatra BPBD is faced with complex challenges that can affect the performance of its employees.

In this context, transformational leadership becomes the main focus, considering the complex dynamics and rapid changes in the world of education today. Transformational leadership does not just include managerial aspects, but also involves the ability to inspire, mobilize and change a shared vision (Silahusada et al., 2022). Leadership is the ability to inspire others to achieve common goals, and today's fast-paced world demands leaders who can challenge the status quo, create a vision and mission for the future, and inspire organizational members, (Robbins et al., 2017).

The relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance can be seen that the results obtained are that there is a very significant positive relationship between transformational leadership style and employee performance, meaning that the higher the transformational leadership possessed by the company, the higher the employee performance will be (Armansyah, 2020).

The Kutambaru District Office has a crucial role in providing population administration services in its area. As an agency responsible for services, the Kutambaru District Office is faced with complex challenges that can affect the performance of its employees. According to the author's initial observations through observations and interviews with several employees, the phenomenon that occurs at the Kutambaru District Office is the complexity of handling community problems related to population documents that occur in Kutambaru.

To measure the level of transformational leadership, there are four components that must be present (Shalahuddin, 2016), namely:

1. Idealized influence (ideal influence)

A tenacious, persistent and intelligent leader. And able to demonstrate vision and mission, as well as exemplify good morals. So as to foster sympathy and empathy from subordinates towards the leader. An ideal figure who can set an example and can be imitated.

2. Intellectual stimulation (intellectual stimulation)

As time progresses, leaders will be faced with new problems. Leaders here are required to innovate, at this point leaders must use knowledge to create innovation.

3. Individual consideration (individual consideration)

Transformational leaders consider what their subordinates need. Here the leader acts as a mentor or coach, this kind of application will determine the strengths and weaknesses of his subordinates.

4. Inspiration motivation (inspiration motivation)

Leaders who have standards that are above average and can direct or target subordinates so that they can achieve that average. And before reaching that level, the leader motivates them to be consistent in the achievement process.

According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2016) employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out main tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been established or are applicable in the organization.

To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely:

1. Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
2. Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.

3. Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.
4. Cooperate with other people at work.

The purpose of this research is to analyze and determine the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance in Kutambaru District. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The type of research that will be used is quantitative associative, namely research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2018). In this research, the exogenous variable is transformational leadership (X), while the endogenous variable is employee performance (Y). This research was carried out at the Kutambaru District Office. This research was carried out from March 2024 to June 2024. Population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn, (Sugiyono, 2018). The population in this study were all employees of the Kutambaru District Office, totaling 15 people with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

Status	Amount
Civil servants	8
Honorary/Task Force	7
Total	15

According to (Sugiyono, 2018) the sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. If the population is large, and it is impossible for researchers to study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds, energy and time, then researchers can use samples taken from that population. In this research the author used the entire population, namely the total number of employees as many as 15 people.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid.

Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r\text{-alpha} > r\text{-table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r\text{-alpha} < r\text{-table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Transformational leadership

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Transformational Leadership (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Transformational leadership	15	3.00	5.00	4,1500	,51582
Performance	15	3.00	5.00	4.1167	,57373
Valid N (listwise)	15				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess transformational leadership and employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office as above average, with mean values of 4,150 and 4,116 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.515 for transformational leadership and 0.573 for employee

performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perceptions, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Transformational Leadership Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KK1	0.882 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK2	0.775 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK3	0.882 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KK4	0.684 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the transformational leadership variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.514 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the transformational leadership variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.767 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.638 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.829 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.765 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on employee performance variables have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.514 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the statements for employee performance variables are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61.

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Transformational leadership	0.825	4
Employee Performance	0.743	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the transformational leadership and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	8,649	,851		,763	,459
1 Leadership Transformational	,836	,204	,751	4,104	,001

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 8.649 + 0.836X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 8.649 means that if there is no transformational leadership, then there is an employee performance of 8.649 points. The transformational leadership regression coefficient is 0.836, meaning that transformational leadership influences an increase in employee performance of 0.836 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,751a	,564	,531	,39298

a. Predictors: (Constant), Transformational Leadership

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.531 or 53.10%, which means that transformational leadership has a high influence on employee performance, while the remaining 46.90% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office

Ha: There is an influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8,649	,851		,763	,459
1 Transformational leadership	,836	,204	,751	4,104	,001

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 4.104 > t table 1.753, with a significance value of 0.001 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between transformational leadership on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office .

The adjusted R Square value is 0.531 or 53.10%, which means that transformational leadership has a high influence on employee performance, while the remaining 46.90% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance, these findings are in line with research results (Tucunan et al.,

2014) which show that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence between transformational leadership and employee performance; (2) there is a positive and significant influence between transformational leadership and employee motivation; (3) there is a significant positive influence between employee motivation and employee performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that Transformational Leadership (interpersonal relationships) has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Office with a calculated t value of $4.104 > t \text{ table } 1,753$, with a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. These results indicate that if relationships between employees are improved, employee performance tends to increase. The relationship between the influence of Transformational Leadership and Employee Performance shows that it has a significant influence. This means that an increase in transformational leadership can directly improve employee performance significantly.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the analysis and conclusions of this research, the following are several suggestions that can be given to the Kutambaru District Office to improve employee performance through increasing Transformational Leadership:

1. Institutions need to focus on improving relationships between employees to improve employee performance. This can be done by holding unusual leadership practices that support social interaction, such as team-building, gatherings, and other events that encourage collaboration and communication. Additionally, it is important to create a friendly and supportive work environment, where employees feel comfortable sharing ideas and contributing.
2. Institutions need to hold ongoing training and development programs to improve employee performance. Training that is structured and appropriate to job requirements will help employees develop the skills needed for better performance. Mentoring and coaching programs can also be implemented to provide direct guidance from more experienced employees.

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